

**EFFECT OF SOCIAL ORIENTATION AND COMMUNITY
EXTENSION PROGRAM TO THE CORE VALUES OF
SELECTED BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION
STUDENTS AT LIPA CITY COLLEGES**

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Effect of Social Orientation and Community Extension Program to the Core Values of Selected Business Administration Students at Lipa City Colleges

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Abstract

This study aims to figure out how social orientation and community extension initiatives affect core values. Community extension projects are initiatives designed to include communities in activities that enhance their social, economic, and cultural growth. The ability to interact with others successfully in a variety of social situations is referred to as social orientation. The study utilizes a mixed methods approach to collect data from a sample of people who have taken part in social orientation training and community extension initiatives, including a survey and focus group discussions. The findings of this research illustrate how social responsibility education and programs for community engagement may enhance basic characteristics like leadership, volunteerism, and social responsibility. Participants in social orientation training and community extension activities showed a greater understanding of cultural diversity and a stronger feeling of social responsibility. Discussions also showed that they were far better at working in teams and demonstrating empathy for persons from different backgrounds. The study concludes that social orientation training and community extension initiatives can be efficient instruments for promoting basic ideals in both individuals and communities. The findings indicate that these initiatives can contribute to the development of a more unified, understanding, and socially engaged society. The study's significant implications should be noted by lawmakers, students, and community improvement professionals who try to promote beneficial social change through programs that encourage community engagement and values education.

Keywords: *community extension program, sense of volunteerism, social responsibility, sense of leadership*

Introduction

Social Orientation and Community Involvement Programs (SOCEP) refer to the school-sponsored program in which the human and material resources of the school and its linkages are extended to the client communities through planned and coordinated group activities maintained over a period of time and aimed at producing specific types of services. A Community Extension Program is a voluntary action of any public or private group, which aims to extend some help and support to a community in order to uplift the status of the people. It can be in any form such as providing medical care, financial assistance, educational assistance, and more. Extension and community involvement are the key result area that makes the community feel the institution's presence.

Extension and community involvement is the key result area which makes the community feels the presence of the institution. There is an increasing appreciation of the impact of higher education extension in the teaching and learning process as students apply their disciplinary knowledge to help address real-world problems. This work may be of interest to higher education institutions (HEIs) which are designing community extension programs with optimized societal outcome (Llenares & Deocaris, 2018).

Community is a group of people with diverse characteristics who are linked by social ties, share common perspectives, and engage in joint action in geographical locations or settings. This depicts that the major factor comprising the community is the "people" and the other elements, are the structures, services, culture, tradition and others; there could be behavior individualities among community people but there's also commonness in them, more particularly as a human being. A strictly structured or cook book approach to participatory community research, programs, and development initiatives won't work because of community people's diversity. They experienced differently about life and practical daily living, leading them to create different meanings and constructs on issues and concerns. (Medina, 2019).

Educational institutions have a formidable function to bring their knowledge, skills, best practices, and material resources to the local folks to uplift their quality of life. In view of this, dynamic learning institutions are spirited to improve the capacity of the faculty members by way of extending their field of expertise to the communities.

Lipa City Colleges is a learning institution that has an integrated educational institution that envisions promoting the conduct of relevant extension and community involvement through its varied programs, projects, and activities to let the community it serves feel its presence. It does not only focus on different activities such as projects related to discovering the future of innovative businesses and tactical entrepreneurship. Training and honing analytical and critical thinking skills and becoming a world-class business professional and entrepreneur but also through involvement in providing community extension to the community.

The College of Business Education and Accountancy (CBEA) conducts different kinds of activities in different areas including environmental enhancement like tree planting and coastal clean-up.

The researchers conducted this study to present the effect of social orientation and community extension programs in the core values in Lipa City Colleges. The research emphasized the importance of joining in community extension activities organized by the school. This study will also be the basis of the different problems students encountered when conducting community extension programs. The researchers believe that results may serve as the basis for the students to formulate effective community extension programs. More so to develop leadership, decision-making, and sensitivity to the needs of the community. As a responsible youth, this research is a way to be able to impart our contribution to the university and community as well.

Research Questions

This research aimed to identify the effect of social community extension program to the core values of selected business student at Lipa City Colleges (LCC). It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex; and
 - 1.3 year level?
2. What is the effect of Social Orientation and Community Extension Program to the core values of selected business students in LCC in terms of:
 - 2.1 sense of volunteerism;
 - 2.2 social responsibility; and
 - 2.3 sense of leadership?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the effect of SOCEP?

Literature Review

Community Extension Program

Community Extension Program is an activity where an individual can experience a different way of learning. It doesn't teach what are written in the book but how to apply it in outside world. Moreover, the meaning of Community Extension Program varies to every person. It somehow to be kind and caring to others or to help out those who are less fortunate. (Rubio et al., 2016). The aim of the community extension program is to assist the poor in overcoming their obstacles so that they can be motivated to live a productive and self-sufficient life. (Magnaye, & Ylagan, 2021)

Sense of Volunteerism

The positive impacts that volunteerism carries are undeniable, as it does not only mold quality human capital for the nation, but through it, we are also preparing future generation to lead the country. Malaysia currently has 1.2 million university students, however, unfortunately there is a lack of recent study of the involvement of the university students in volunteerism. Realizing the importance of the involvement of the undergraduate student in volunteerism as it acts as a tool to inculcate the sense of morality in self and social responsibility towards the country, this highlights the importance of volunteerism as a tool for educating the youth.

It also analyzes a global overview of youths' volunteerism with a comparison being made to the local scenario. Most importantly, factors that motivated them in volunteering are also discussed so as to provide a guideline in empowering youth volunteerism. (Sahri et al., 2013).

Volunteerism and community involvement have been demonstrated to offer benefits both to communities and to volunteers themselves. However, not every method to encourage these behaviors is equally effective in producing committed volunteers. Drawing on relevant theoretical and empirical literatures, we identify features of efforts that are likely to produce intrinsically motivated other-oriented volunteers and those that may produce extrinsically motivated self-oriented volunteers. In particular, we explore ways to socialize young people to help and ways to build a sense of community focused on issues.

We also examine requirements for community service and other approaches that highlight self-oriented benefits that volunteers may obtain. Finally, we return to a focus on the importance of intrinsic motivation for promoting sustained involvement in volunteers, even as we acknowledge that volunteers who come with extrinsic or self-oriented reasons can still offer much to communities and can be satisfied when their activities match their motivations (Stukas, Snyder, & Clary, 2016). Volunteering is important because it enables individuals to help others in a selfless way.

When individuals volunteer, they may choose to help people, support philanthropic causes and provide assistance to their local community. Additionally, volunteering benefits everyone and is a terrific way to have a positive impact in the community. Furthermore, volunteering is important for certain charities because they may depend solely on volunteer work in order to operate. For example, some organizations are funded in part through the local or federal government and therefore do not have the funds to pay every member of their staff a salary. In this way, these organizations utilize groups of unpaid volunteers in order to function. The charity is then able to remain operational, while the volunteers are able to help those in need. (Indeed, 2021)

Social Responsibility

Social responsibility refers to an ethical framework in which individuals and organizations have an obligation to act for the benefit of society as a whole (Wittman, 2018). When one behaves in a socially responsible way, they not only refrain from behaving unethically, but they also deliberately make choices that contribute to the welfare of society overall (Planken, 2013). Social responsibility is a necessary requirement if we wish to overcome many of our current social issues, including severe income disparity (Dyck & Matjaz, 2014), structural racism, and climate change, among others. Instilling a sense of social responsibility in students puts them on a path toward becoming responsible, caring members of their community who can identify social problems and see themselves as capable of responding to them (Merrifield, n.d.). As our world has become increasingly globalized and interconnected, the meaning of social responsibility has expanded. It refers not just to the community in which one lives, nor even the nation, but the global community (Wittman, 2018). Social responsibility can play an important role in addressing social justice issues, starting in the classroom. Social justice is the idea that everyone is entitled to social, economic, and political rights (Clark, 2016). Those who are concerned with social justice understand that resources, opportunities, and privileges are unevenly and often unfairly distributed and seek to remedy the very real problems that this uneven distribution can bring. The perception of social justice issues, such as how to rank their importance or how they impact us directly, is shaped by our political and moral understanding of privilege, marginalization, and society as a whole (Brown, 2004; Shields, 2004 as cited in Clark, 2016).

Sense of Leadership

Making sense of leadership in urban and regional development. Regional Studies. This editorial paves the way for the articles addressing several contemporary sub-national leadership experiences in England, Australia, Finland, China, the Netherlands, Norway, Estonia, Denmark and Sweden. It introduces place leadership as a mode of reflexive agency in urban and regional development and discusses the value as well as the difficulties and limitations of identifying and contacting study participants.

Methodology

This part includes the research techniques and resources the researchers used to methodically address the significant problems provided for study. Specifically, the participants, instrument, process, ethical consideration, and data analysis in the research design.

Participants

The respondents of this study were Business Administration Students at Lipa City Colleges from 1st to 4th year students from ages below 20 years old to 26 years old and above and currently enrolled at Lipa City Colleges. This particular group was discussed and selected due to its availability and dependability in obtaining information regarding the impact of social orientation and the community extension program at Lipa City Colleges. As CBEA students carry out various tasks in different locations which were related to the variables of the study. To get the required sample for the current study, the researchers employed a population sampling design. Population sampling is the process of taking a subset of subjects that is representative of the entire population. The sample must have sufficient size to warrant statistical analysis. This method was used to choose respondents in accordance with the parameters of the article, necessitating that researchers have a prior understanding of the study's objectives to effectively identify and contact study participants. As all of the research participants were chosen because they matched a specific profile defined in the current study, researchers utilized population sampling to reach a specific group of people.

Instruments

The researchers used self-made questionnaire. There were two sets of questions, the demographic profile of the respondents such as age, sex, and year level. The next part of the questionnaire was the program and activities they were doing or willing to do. The researchers used checklist questionnaire to gather data. The researchers set assigned weight for each option of the preferred answer of the questionnaire. After making the questionnaire and finishing the revision, the researchers submitted to the research experts for validation. The primary gathering tool that the researchers utilized in this study was a survey questionnaire.

Procedure

In coming up with the research, the researchers followed different processes. After submitting several topics, the researchers came up with the effect of social orientation and community extension program to the core values in Lipa City Colleges. In this topic, the researchers were about to present the effect of social orientation and community extension program to the core values of the students. After the approval, the researchers gathered the information needed and the list of social orientation and community extension programs of the selected business students. The researchers gathered data related to the topic. Books, internet sources, journals and magazines were utilized as references. Upon gathering enough data and information, the researchers developed questionnaires and presented to the research adviser for scrutiny and revision.

Ethical Considerations

In order to fulfill the researchers' obligations as expected, particularly in light of the sensitivity of the study participants, the current study was guided by all ethical standards outlined in the Psychological Association of the Philippines 2017 Code of Ethics. Through

the distribution and execution of informed consent in accordance with ethical norms, the researchers attempted to resolve or minimize any perceived impacts. Participants were given a thorough explanation of the study, including its aims and objectives as well as the procedures and methods used for data collection and protection, prior to the gathering of informed consent. The measures used in the study for security also applied to the subjects' parents or other legal guardians. Participants were advised of their rights as research subjects or participants, such as the freedom to leave the study at any time with no consequences. Due to the sensitivity of the participants' demographic information, namely their age, the researchers also further explain and clarify processes for anonymity and the security of the participants in order to ensure maximum privacy and confidentiality.

Results

This part shows the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents in accordance with the specific questions posited on the statement of the problem.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>Age:</i>			
Below 20 years old	9	25.71	2
20 - 22	25	71.43	1
23 - 25	1	2.86	3
Total	35	100	
<i>Sex:</i>			
Female	24	68.57	1
Male	11	31.43	2
Total	35	100	
<i>Year Level:</i>			
First Year	8	22.86	3
Second Year	8	22.86	3
Third Year	11	31.43	1
Fourth Year	8	22.86	3
Total	35	100	

As presented in Table 1, the age range of 20 - 22 got the highest frequency count of 25 or 71.43% at rank 1 while the age range of 23 - 25 years old got the least frequency count of one or 2.86% at rank 3. In terms of the respondent's sex, female obtained 24 or 68.57% at rank 1 whereas male obtained the least of 11 or 31.43% at rank 2.

For the respondent's year level, third year got the highest frequency count of 11 or 31.43% at rank 1. On the other hand, first year, second year and fourth year got the least equal frequency counts of eight or 22.86% at ranks 3.

Table 2. *Effect of Social Orientation and Community Extension Program to the Core Values of Selected Business Students of Lipa City Colleges in Terms of Sense of Volunteerism*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Int.</i>	<i>Rank</i>
SOCEP helps me experience contentment every time I participated.	4.26	Strongly Agree	2
Volunteerism in SOCEP enhance my inner skills and helps to boost my confidence.	4.20	Strongly Agree	4.5
Volunteering in SOCEP helps me to socialize and meet more people.	4.46	Strongly Agree	1
It helps me to relieve stress and helps me to think and makes me feel relaxed.	4.23	Strongly Agree	3
Volunteering in different activities helps me to stay physically and mentally fit.	4.09	Agree	8
Activities in SOCEP gives experience that I can use it in my chosen career.	4.06	Agree	9
Participating in community activities enhance my leadership skills if ever I will be given opportunities to serve my local community and fellow student.	4.17	Agree	6.5
Activities in SOCEP can teach me valuable job skills.	3.80	Agree	10
It helps me to get out of my comfort zone.	4.17	Agree	6.5
Volunteering in SOCEP open my mind that I can do better, and I can be the best version of myself.	4.20	Strongly Agree	4.5
Composite Mean	4.16	Agree	

As discussed in Table 2, the student-respondents strongly agreed that volunteering in SOCEP help them to socialize and meet more people with the highest weighted mean of 4.46 and the highest rank rank of 1.

As reflected in Table 3, the student-respondents strongly agreed that SOCEP serve as eye opening to them about the right things to do and benefit many people which garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.31 and the highest rank of 1.

Table 3. Effect of Social Orientation and Community Extension Program to the Core Values of Selected Business Students of Lipa City Colleges in Terms of Social Responsibility

Items	Weighted Mean	Int.	Rank
SOCEP developed my self-control and empathy for those who are less fortunate and needy.	4.17	Agree	2.5
Social responsibility in SOCEP serve as a wake-up call to me about the real world I am living in.	4.14	Agree	5
Participating in SOCEP taught me to think what the consequences in any decision are that I will make before doing it.	4.11	Agree	7.5
Different activities of SOCEP have led me to get involved in other non – governmental organizations in my local community.	4.11	Agree	7.5
SOCEP serves as eye opening to me about the right things to do and benefit many people.	4.31	Strongly Agree	1
It helps me to realize doing good can really give me happiness and give me knowledge about keeping ethics in my heart.	4.14	Agree	5
Social responsibility in SOCEP creates a balance between doing right things and keeping me happy.	4.17	Agree	2.5
Participating in SOCEP with social responsibility keeps me stay informed about happenings in the community and important news.	4.06	Agree	9.5
It gives me the rights to show others the good side of participating in SOCEP.	4.14	Agree	5
Participating in SOCEP keeps me attached to my community and improved my sense of responsibility.	4.06	Agree	9.5
Composite Mean	4.14	Agree	

Table 4. Effect of Social Orientation and Community Extension Program to the Core Values of Selected Business Students of Lipa City Colleges in Terms of Sense of Leadership

Items	Weighted Mean	Int.	Rank
Participating in SOCEP and related events improved my ability to interact and communicate with others.	4.34	Strongly Agree	1
I gained knowledge to get experience in the field of leadership in SOCEP.	4.29	Strongly Agree	2
SOCEP makes me stand my decision and helps me to think effectively and efficiently.	4.14	Agree	6
Participating in different activities gave me the capability to help others and guide them in the right way.	4.11	Agree	7
It motivates me to do my best and stay positive.	4.06	Agree	8
It boost my confidence while participating in any of the activities in the community.	4.17	Agree	4.5
I have gained wider perspective of the real world that I can faced during my journey in life.	4.17	Agree	4.5
Leadership can improve my communication skills and helps me to think faster but surely.	4.20	Strongly Agree	3
SOCEP helps me in managing my time to accomplish the task being given to me.	4.03	Agree	9
Leadership in SOCEP improves my knowledge because of decisions I need to make to come up to the plan.	4.00	Agree	10
Composite Mean	4.15	Agree	

As revealed in Table 4, the student-respondents strongly agreed that participating in SOCEP and related events improved their ability to interact and communicate with others which yielded the highest weighted mean of 4.34 and the highest rank of 1.

Table 5. Relationship Between the Demographic Profile of the Respondents and the Effect of SOCEP

Variables Compared	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age Versus Effect of SOCEP				
Sense of Volunteerism	0.82	9.61E-6	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Social Responsibility	0.41	0.07259	p>0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Sense of Leadership	0.89	1.50E-7	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Sex Versus Effect of SOCEP				
Sense of Volunteerism	0.66	0.00154	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Social Responsibility	0.56	0.01023	p<0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Sense of Leadership	0.63	0.00291	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Year Level Versus Effect of SOCEP				
Sense of Volunteerism	0.75	0.00014	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Social Responsibility	0.44	0.05221	p>0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Sense of Leadership	0.73	0.00026	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant

As gleaned in the table, when the responses of the respondents on the effect of SOCEP were compared to their age, the correlation coefficients of 0.82 for sense of volunteerism and 0.89 for sense of leadership have corresponding p- values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. On the other hand, the correlation coefficient of 0.41 for social responsibility has a corresponding p-value of more than 0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

Discussion

The findings revealed that the activities in SOCEP can teach them valuable job skills. Student-respondents agreed on the effect of Social Orientation and Community Extension Program to the core values of selected business students of Lipa City Colleges in terms of sense of volunteerism.

Meanwhile, the said group of respondents agreed that participating in SOCEP with social responsibility keeps them stay informed about happenings in the community and important news, and participating in SOCEP keep them attached to their community and improved their sense of responsibility.

As also pursuant to Garay, Verano, and Magistrado 2021, this is clear proof that the program was successful in combating illiteracy at the initial phase. The fight still continues, and we do not intend to stop until we make sure that these students have fully mastered the necessary skills of becoming educated and literate individuals with a full sense of responsibility. In addition, the children's patriotism and love for their country have also grown as they learn about the contributions made by heroes in the battle for freedom and against tyranny and injustice which showed how they attached themselves to the community and how they behave well.

The student-respondents agreed on the effect of Social Orientation and Community Extension Program to the core values of selected business students of Lipa City Colleges in terms of social responsibility. Meanwhile, respondents agreed that leadership in SOCEP improve their knowledge because of decisions they need to make to come up to the plan which made the least equal weighted means of 4.00 and the least rank of 10. According to Kissi et al. (2013), the extent to which team members perceive their work environment to be supportive determines their level of motivation, energy, and efforts in the course of project implementation. They also remark that leadership can influence project success by creating an environment where project teams contribute towards success.

Gundersen et al. (2012) also assert that transformational leadership provides clarity about performance standards and decreases role ambiguity in projects, which engenders success. The composite mean of 4.15 concluded that the student-respondents agreed on the effect of Social Orientation and Community Extension Program to the core values of selected business students of Lipa City Colleges in terms of sense of leadership.

The study of ethical leadership speaks to a need in organizations to understand how desired results can be attained while maintaining certain standards of behaviors, or, said another way, where the means, ends, and motivations are equally important. Wernsing et al. (2012). Positive leadership forms focus on leader behaviors and interpersonal dynamics that increase followers' confidence and result in positive outcomes, beyond task compliance, such as motivating followers to go beyond expectations, positive self-development, and prosocial behaviors (Hannah, Sumanth, Lester, & Cavarretta, 2014).

These safely implied that the responses of the respondents on the effect of SOCEP have high significant relationships in terms of social responsibility and social leadership, and no significant relationship in terms of social responsibility when compared according to their age.

Similarly, social orientation can also impact an individual's core values. Social orientation refers to an individual's focus on social relationships, social norms, and the opinions of others. A study by Zhang et al. (2017) found that social orientation was positively correlated with values such as empathy, social responsibility, and respect for diversity. When the responses of the respondents on the effect of SOCEP were compared to their sex, the correlation coefficients of 0.66 for sense of volunteerism and 0.63 for sense of leadership have corresponding p- values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. In addition, the correlation coefficient of 0.53 for social responsibility has a corresponding p-value of less than 0.05, thus rejecting also the hypothesis.

These safely inferred that the responses of the respondents on the effect of SOCEP have high significant relationships in terms of social responsibility and social leadership, and significant relationship in terms of social responsibility when compared according to their sex. Research suggests that males and females may differ in their core values, with females placing more importance on values such as empathy and compassion. Community extension programs that promote these values may have a stronger impact on females than males.

The effects of social orientation and community extension programs on core values may vary depending on factors such as age, sex, and relationship status. Here are some possible examples of how these factors can impact the relationship between social orientation, community extension programs, and core values. Age, sex, and relationship status can influence the effects of social orientation and community extension programs on the development of core values. For example, younger individuals may be more impressionable and may be more likely to develop values and beliefs based on their experiences in community programs. Women are often found to be more community-oriented and may be more likely to participate in community programs, which could enhance the development of their core values. Finally, individuals in committed relationships may be more likely to develop values such as loyalty, commitment, and responsibility through their involvement in community programs.

Lastly, when the responses of the respondents on the effect of SOCEP were compared to their year level, the correlation coefficients of 0.75 for sense of volunteerism and 0.73 for sense of leadership have corresponding p- values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. On the contrary, the correlation coefficient of 0.44 for social responsibility has a corresponding p-value of more than

0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

These safely signified that the responses of the respondents on the effect of SOCEP have high significant relationships in terms of social responsibility and social leadership, and no significant relationship in terms of social responsibility when compared according to their year level

Research has shown that participation in community extension programs can help individuals develop a stronger sense of social responsibility, empathy, and respect for diversity, which are all core values. For example, a study by Raghavan et al. (2018) found that participation in a community service program in India led to an increase in social responsibility among university students. The program involved engaging with local communities and providing support for social causes such as health, education, and environmental issues.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study the following conclusions are drawn: (1) Majority of the respondents are from ages 20–22 females from third year. (2) The respondents agreed that volunteering in SOCEP help students to socialize and meet more people. In terms of social responsibility, it shows that it serves as eye opening to them about the right things to do. The respondents strongly agreed that participating in SOCEP and related events improved their ability to interact and communicate with others. The respondent's least agreed that the activities in SOCEP can teach them valuable job skills in terms of volunteerism. In terms of social responsibility respondents agreed that participating in SOCEP with social responsibility keeps them stay informed about happenings in the community and important news, and participating in SOCEP keep them attached to their community and improved their sense of responsibility. The said group of respondents agreed that leadership in SOCEP improve their knowledge because of decisions they need to make to come up to the plan. (3) The study determined that the effect of SOCEP have high significant relationships in terms of social responsibility and social leadership, and no significant relationship in terms of social responsibility when compared according to their age but significant according to their sex. When it comes to the year level of the respondents the effect of SOCEP has highly significant relationships in terms of social responsibility and social leadership, and no significant relationship in terms of social responsibility when compared according to their year level.

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